

Determinants Affecting Students' Intention To Start-Up Business: A Case Study Of Universities In Dong Nai Province

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 12, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Student, Intention, Start-Up, Business, Enterprise, and LHU</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5277697</p>	<p><i>Nowadays, a new start-up flow has appeared and made a bold impression in Vietnam despite the difficulties. The start-up market in Vietnam is still among the top 3 thriving start-up markets in Southeast Asia, along with Thailand and Indonesia. This start-up proves that the Vietnamese start-up market is alive and has potential for development. Besides, students start a business no longer a strange thing, but not all students can start a business while still at universities. Because they lack investment money, lack human resources, or do not have the correct student start-up idea? Whatever the reason, students who dare business are very welcome. To help students understand about starting-up business. Therefore, the authors surveyed 800 students studying at three universities in Dong Nai province. In addition, the article explores critical factors affecting students' intention to start-up business with one percent significance. The paper was applying structural equation modeling (SEM). Finally, the authors had policy recommendations to enhance students' intention to start a business in Dong Nai province.</i></p>

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is playing an increasingly important role in sustainable development and many countries. Many studies have demonstrated the contribution of start-ups to the national economic growth, primarily through job creation and increasing the diversity of the economy by Begley, W. L. (2015). Therefore, promoting entrepreneurship has become an essential goal in the economic development strategy of many countries. Small and medium enterprises are the majority and primary types of contributions in the economy. They are accounting for nearly 97% of the total number of enterprises in the country. Besides, they have been employing up to 51% of social workers and contributing to the economy more than 40% of GDP... The amount of taxes and fees these enterprises have paid to the State has increased 18.4 times after ten years. The above results have confirmed the importance and value that private enterprises bring. However, research results showed that 100 people who have started a business in the past two years, 80%, are at risk of dissolution in the first year of operation by Bird, B. H. (2018).

The main reason comes from the lack of capital (accounting for 40%), lack of knowledge on management and administration of small and medium enterprises (accounting for 50%), lack of practical experience in the business environment (accounting for 30%). Vietnam is witnessing the rise of a younger generation of entrepreneurs. They are confident, determined, strong to create jobs for themselves and many others. However, for young entrepreneurs to start a business successfully, they need the companionship of many organizations and individuals by Fitzsimmons, J.R., and Douglas, E.J. (2011).

However, there are still many difficulties and challenges ahead for the national spirit of entrepreneurship. Just talking about start-ups makes many people wonder. This community has just formed in our country not long ago. The scale is still small. There is a particular development and success, but unfortunately, many Vietnamese start-up businesses have registered their trade abroad and develop overseas markets and products. If so, how can the national spirit of entrepreneurship be promoted when one of the crucial elements of national creativity begins with the start-up enterprise. Therefore, the article explores five factors affecting students' intention to start a business in Dong Nai province.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Intention to a start-up business (ISB)

Evans, D. E., and Hanson, M. T. (2013) showed that the Start-up business: Starting a business is an individual (alone or with others) taking advantage of a new business opportunity, or a working attitude that promotes independence, self-control, creativity, innovation, and acceptance. Risk to create new value in the existing business. Start-up is a term that refers to companies that are in the start-up stage in general, relates

narrowly to companies that form ideas during the start-up stage. Entrepreneurship is a start-up process based on creating or applying research results, technical solutions, technologies, and management solutions to improve productivity, quality, and added value of products, commodities and capable of rapid growth by Trevelyan, R. (2011).

Intention to start a business: According to Ekpoh, U. I., & Edet, A. O. (2011), the entrepreneurial intention is immediately aware of awareness before performing a behavior. An intent represents the degree of commitment about the conduct to serve in the future. There are many different authors' definitions of the intention to start a business. But they are all unified in terms of content. According to Chupta, V. K. & Bhawe, S. M. (2017), entrepreneurial intention is the commitment to start by creating a new business. Garis, R. D. (2016) suggested that people who intend to start a business are individuals who are willing to pioneer in seizing attractive business opportunities that they perceive. Starting a business will occur if an individual has a positive attitude, thoughts, and intentions about that action. A firm intention is a premise that drives the effort to start a business by Garali, S. F. (2013), who argued that people who intend to start a company would be the ones to take risks and take necessary actions when they perceive the signal of business opportunities.

Start-up support(SS)

Entrepreneurship support includes internal influences such as opinions from family, friends, colleagues, and external forces, which are social trends by Trueger, N. D. (2013). In the view of Brazeal, D. F. (2014), entrepreneurship support, especially the opinion of relatives, plays a significant role, especially in collectivist cultures. In a collectivist culture, there is always mutual influence among family members; individual interests come after collective interests. Therefore, in a collectivist culture, the subjective norm factor positively affects an individual's thoughts and attitudes by Linan, F. W. (2016). Vietnam is a country with a traditional family culture, so the independence of each individual is lower than in Western countries. Studies have shown that the entrepreneurship support factor affects students' intention to start a business. From that, we have the following hypothesis H1:

Hypothesis H1: Start-up support (SS) positively impacting students' intention to start-up business in Dong Nai province.

Feasibility perception(FP)

Perceived feasibility is the degree to which an individual perceives how easy or difficult it is; controlled, restricted, or not when performing a behavior, is an individual's degree of confidence in their ability to perform Luthje, C. N. (2014). In this study, it was an individual's perception of the possibility of starting a business. The intention to start a business will decrease when it is perceived as not feasible. Feasibility gives hope to ideas, determination to turn ideas into reality by Chen, Y. and He, Y. (2011). Studies have shown that the perceived feasibility factor influences students' intention to start a business by Mahadalle, A., Kaplan, B. (2017). From that, we have the following hypothesis H2:

Hypothesis H2: Feasibility perception (FP) positively impacting students' intention to start-up business in Dong Nai province.

Educational environment (EE)

An entrepreneurship education environment involves programs, extra-curricular lectures, or courses that provide students with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes to pursue a career in business by Maat, S. M., and Mohd, N. S. (2015). Many empirical studies have verified that the educational environment of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial intention have a positive relationship. The entrepreneurship education environment equips students with the necessary business knowledge and skills to build an entrepreneurial spirit. Besides, educational background helps them dare to face business difficulties in the future, helps them become entrepreneurs when having basic knowledge of business management while reducing risk barriers by Selvarajah, C. H. & Meyer, D. A. (2018). Therefore, an entrepreneurship education environment effectively inspires students with entrepreneurial intentions and entrepreneurial actions and increases the proportion of students who dare to take risks in business by Wapero, A. C. & Sokol, L. G. (2019). Studies have shown that environmental factors in entrepreneurship education influence students' intention to start a business. From that, we have the following hypothesis H3:

Hypothesis H3: Educational environment (EE) positively impacting students' intention to start-up business in Dong Nai province.

Personality traits(PT)

Personality traits refer to personal characteristics that speak to an entrepreneur's personality. This factor is predictive of entrepreneurial intention by Zerbinati, S. D. and Laham, A. V. (2017). However, Wongnaa, C. A., and Seyram, Z. K. (2014) argued that personality traits affect entrepreneurial intention in three ways: the need to achieve, locus of internal control, and risk-taking. Success reflects the individual's desire for success that affects the choice to start a business. According to Tauch, M. F. (2017) research results, the need to achieve is the strongest predictor of business intention. The locus of internal control: represents an individual's confidence and power in controlling business behavior. Studies have shown that the personality trait factor influences students' intention to start a business. From that, we have the following hypothesis H4:

Hypothesis H4: Personality traits (PT) positively impacting students' intention to start-up business in Dong Nai province.

Access finance (AF)

Capital is an important factor throughout the business process as well as businesses. When starting a business, students often face the problem of raising capital to invest in their ideas. If access to finance is easy, it will increase students' chances of starting a business and vice versa. According to the research results of Seibert, G. T. (2017). Martin, J. J. and McNally, M. K. (2013) had shown that the factor Access to finance influences students' intention to start a business. Capital: The ability to access investment capital for a business idea. If access to finance is easy, it will increase students' chances of starting a business. Duysters, M. C (2016) showed that the capital factor directly influences students' entrepreneurial intention. From that, we have the following hypothesis H5:

Hypothesis H5: Access finance (AF) positively impacting students' intention to start-up business in Dong Nai province.

Based on the theory and research on entrepreneurship, the authors propose the following research model:

Source: Researchers discovered

FIGURE 1
A RESEARCH MODEL FOR FACTORS AFFECTING STUDENTS' INTENTION TO START-UP BUSINESS IN DONG NAI PROVINCE

METHODS OF RESEARCH

In this study, the authors presented research methods including research process, description of research sampling method, qualitative research, quantitative research, construction of expected scale, correction of and data analysis methods.

Source: Researchers proposed

FIGURE 2
A RESEARCH PROCESS FOR FACTORS AFFECTING STUDENTS' INTENTION TO START-UP BUSINESS IN DONG NAI PROVINCE

Qualitative research aims to consider whether the scales used in the study are suitable for studying students' entrepreneurial intentions. And at the same time, evaluate the use of terms in the questionnaire and clarify each question's meaning before the formal study by Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., & Black, W. (2010). The authors' group conducts group discussions with 15 participants who are experts in the field of entrepreneurship.

Based on the comments, the authors had the survey questionnaire built after testing to test the adjustment of language presentation, the formal questionnaire used for subsequent quantitative research.

Formal quantitative research was carried out by survey method of 800 students studying at three universities in Dong Nai province. When the results are available, the authors synthesized statistics based on the

information obtained from the survey. Data processing, reliability testing of each scale component through Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Testing of research hypotheses by structural equation model (SEM) with SPSS 20.0 and Amos. The quantitative study was conducted with an expected sample size of $n =$ students studying at three universities in Dong Nai province from July 2020 to December 2020. The authors used a convenient sampling method to pick a sample, but 771 samples were processed, leaving 29 samples unprocessed. Finally, the authors had conclusions and recommendations.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Testing of Cronbach's alpha

Code	Intention to a start-up business (ISB)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
ISB1	I am always determined to set up a company in the future	0.949
ISB2	I will try to get my company established soon	0.894
ISB3	I seriously thought about starting my own company	0.946
Cronbach's alpha: 0.952		

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 1 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the intention to a start-up business (ISB) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the intention to a start-up business (ISB) is 0.952, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

Code	Start-up support (SS.)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
SS1	My family will support my decision to start a business	0.954
SS2	My friends will support my decision to start a business	0.964
SS3	The people who are important to me will support my decision to start a business	0.962
SS4	The State has policies to encourage students to start a business	0.948
Cronbach's alpha: 0.968		

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 2 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the start-up support (SS) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the start-up support (SS) is 0.968, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

Code	Feasibility perception (FP)	Cronbach's Alpha
FP1	Students believe in success if they start a business	0.954
FP2	Starting a business is easy for students	0.964
FP3	Starting a business is best to take advantage of students' intellectual advantage	0.967
FP4	Students know how to develop a business project and can become successful entrepreneurs	0.953
Cronbach's alpha: 0.969		

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 3 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the feasibility perception (FP) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the feasibility perception (FP) is 0.969, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

Code	Educational environment (EE)	Cronbach's Alpha
EE1	The university provides the necessary knowledge about entrepreneurship	0.807
EE2	The core curriculum at the university prepares students to start a business	0.816
EE3	The university often organizes entrepreneurship-oriented activities for students	0.852
EE4	The university develops entrepreneurship skills for students	0.809
Cronbach's alpha: 0.860		

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0)

Table 4 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the educational environment (EE) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the academic environment (EE) is 0.860, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

Code	Personality traits (PT)	Cronbach's Alpha
PT1	Students tend to choose careers that requirediscovery, creation	0.879
PT2	Students consider business to be interesting because it challenges the ability to student's ability	0.837
PT3	Students dare to face obstacles and take risks in business	0.889
PT4	Students are qualified to manage businesses	0.876
Cronbach's alpha: 0.899		

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 5 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the personality traits (PT) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the personality traits (PT) is 0.899, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

Code	Access finance (AF)	Cronbach's Alpha
AF1	Students can borrow money from friends and relatives to start a business	0.946
AF2	Students can accumulate capital thanks to saving expenses, working part-time	0.937
AF3	Students can raise capital from other sources such as banks, credit funds	0.946
AF4	Students can raise capital from the national start-up program and sponsors	0.926
Cronbach's alpha: 0.954		

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 6 showed that Cronbach's alpha for the access finance (AF) meets this technique's requirements. Specifically, Cronbach's Alpha values of the access finance (AF) is 0.954, and Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted (>0.6).

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.836
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	18906.101
	df	253
	Sig.	0.000
Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings: Cumulative is 85.333 %		

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0

Table 7 showed that the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy (KMO) is 0.836 (>0.5). This result is consistent with the actual data investigated by 800 students studying at three universities in Dong Nai province.

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos

FIGURE 3
TESTING CFA FOR FACTORS AFFECTING STUDENTS' INTENTION TO START-UP BUSINESS
IN DONG NAI PROVINCE

Figure 3 showed that the assessment of the scale of the students' intention to start-up business in Dong Nai Province including: CMIN/DF = 4.126 (<5.0), GFI = 0.913 (>0.8), TLI = 0.958 (>0.9), CFI = 0.964 (> 0.9) and RMSE = 0.064 (<0.08). The model indicators showed that they are perfect and consistent with both theory and practice in Dong Nai province.

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos

FIGURE 4

TESTING SEM FOR FACTORS AFFECTING STUDENTS' INTENTION TO START-UP BUSINESS IN DONG NAI PROVINCE

Figure 4 showed that the SEM assessment had five factors of the students' intention to start-up business in Dong Nai province with a significance level of 0.01. This result is significant proof for educational managers to apply research results in developing programs of starting-up for students.

Relationships	Unstandardized Estimate	Standardized Estimate	SE.	CR.	P	Results
ISB <--- SS	0.519	0.540	0.031	16.993	***	Accepted
ISB <--- FP	0.096	0.097	0.028	3.373	***	Accepted
ISB <--- EE	0.181	0.161	0.035	5.127	***	Accepted
ISB <--- PT	0.179	0.085	0.056	3.196	0.001	Accepted
ISB <--- AF	0.103	0.109	0.029	3.517	***	Accepted

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos

Table 8 showed five factors of the students' intention to start-up business in Dong Nai province with a significance level of 0.01. The results showed that all five elements in the theoretical model influence the entrepreneurial intention of students in Dong Nai province that are ranked in order of importance from high to low; Start-up support (SS) is 0.540, and Personality traits (PT) is 0.085.

Parameter	SE	SE-SE	Mean	Bias	SE-Bias
ISB <--- SS	0.036	0.000	0.520	0.001	0.001
ISB <--- FP	0.034	0.000	0.090	-0.005	0.001
ISB <--- EE	0.040	0.001	0.176	-0.005	0.001
ISB <--- PT	0.053	0.001	0.171	-0.007	0.001
ISB <--- AF	0.027	0.000	0.100	-0.003	0.000

Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos

Table 9 showed that the bootstrap test results are very good with a sample of 15.000 students studying at three universities in Dong Nai province. These results indicated five factors of the students' intention to start-up business in Dong Nai province with a significance level of 0.01. Based on the theoretical review, a research model was developed for this study. This model has been tested with a sample of 800 students studying at three universities in Dong Nai province. With the obtained results, this study has made positive contributions to entrepreneurial management for students.

CONCLUSION & MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Conclusion

Starting a business has always had a very close relationship with the economic development of a country. The enterprises are vital economic sectors that contribute to economic growth, poverty reduction, and job creation. Besides, a developed economy is thanks to the development in both quantity and quality of enterprises. The study has identified the factors and their influence on students' intention to start a business. These results indicated five factors of the students' intention to start-up business in Dong Nai Province with a significance level of 0.01. Five factors including (1) Start-up support (SS); (2) Feasibility perception (FP); (3) Educational environment (EE); (4) Personality traits (PT) and access finance (AF). Through analysis, five independent factors affect students' intention to start a business in descending order: Start-up support (SS) is 0.540, and personality traits (PT) is 0.085. From the results of this study, the authors would like to propose some managerial implications to help schools, start-up support organizations, and macro-management agencies establish solutions to increase intention start a business of students, as a premise for the promotion of entrepreneurial action of students after graduation as follows.

Managerial implications

(1) Managerial implications for improving the start-up support (SS). It is necessary to improve the ability to support students, create motivation, and stimulate students to develop ideas and act with a confident spirit of "Self-employment". This recommendation can be made through training and equipping business knowledge and skills at the universities. Universities widely disseminate business awareness programs so that individual students can self-assess their business capabilities or condition while developing training courses on business start-up skills for students, giving students more confidence to enter the business field. Besides, universities need to organize seminars, business classes regularly, create playgrounds to develop business start-up ideas. For business training, we recommended developing training programs in the direction of approaching and interacting with business practices, and at the same time adding more training modules on starting a business into the training program framework according to "open direction" for students to participate. The university should have worthy reward policies for lecturers and students who win high prizes in the start-up competition.

(2) Managerial implications for improving the educational environment (EE). Universities need to promote the entrepreneurship intentions of students at the university and the short-term training programs and the Entrepreneurship subject. It is necessary to encourage more seminars, seminars, and extra-curricular activities to connect with students. Entrepreneurs and businesses can equip themselves with entrepreneurial knowledge, recognize business opportunities, and especially look at entrepreneurship more positively. In training, besides competitions in recent years, the school has performed exceptionally well. It is necessary to have mechanisms for start-up ideas to be realized. This recommendation will contribute positively to starting a business through the need for achievement and perceived behavioral control.

(3) Managerial implications for improving the access finance (AF). The State needs to improve business conditions, reduce complicated administrative procedures, make policies transparent, and create favorable conditions for business people to access information and assistance. Strengthen financial support for start-ups through sponsors, start-up investment funds, and business incubators to actively support the training process and promote entrepreneurial business intentions. Besides, to increase students' intention to start a business, universities need to innovate their training programs actively, encourage students to learn about entrepreneurship, start a business and build their capacity. Universities need to teach students about entrepreneurship skills to create their jobs by using their expertise to start-up in the industry or field in which they have in-depth knowledge. Finally, The State should have policies to encourage and support students to start a business in credit with preferential interest rates, exemption policy, and corporate income tax reduction for students commencing a business in the first years after graduation.

(4) Managerial implications for improving the feasibility perception (FP). Universities need to strengthen the propaganda of typical and successful business examples. Examples of entrepreneurs who overcome difficulties, are consistent with business goals, know how to overcome the challenges in business,

and actively change innovation to maintain the company so that students desire to get rich and be motivated to act. In addition, the university leadership should encourage and create opportunities for students to pursue their ideas, equipped with functional infrastructure such as classrooms, machinery, equipment for consulting, information, teaching to best support the start-up. Besides, universities should establish start-up clubs to support start-up students. This support aims to create conditions for students to have the opportunity to exchange, perceive and practice skills, especially skills related to the art of leadership, administration, and group management.

(5) Managerial implications for improving the personality traits (PT). For each student to become an entrepreneur, it is necessary to actively study, hone professional knowledge and skills, and at the same time accumulate capital as well as participate in seeking support to be able to start a business soon. Besides, universities and companies need to be able to research and establish start-up investment funds. These investment funds help students form and develop their entrepreneurial intentions and provide students with accurate, complete, and necessary information about undertakings, policies, corporate law, and markets, investments, and areas of interest to students. After that, investment funds need to provide capital for viable start-up intentions to provide financial support in the initial start-up of students. Finally, to inspire business start-ups to increase the sense of desire to start a business for students, the school should launch and sponsor contests on forming business ideas and writing business plans. Companies should look for entrepreneurial talent, etc. At the same time, we call on sponsors to organize activities to stimulate entrepreneurial spirit for students to increase the feasibility of starting a business.

Finally, this paper's limitations had data collected from 3 universities in Dong Nai province. Besides, the data of 800 students are too few compared to the number of universities. Therefore, the results had not reflected the appropriateness of the research model. Thus, it is necessary to further serve students from other universities in other Vietnam provinces to increase data reliability.

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